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On the cover page from left to right:
Prince Vladimir Monomakh, the Emperor Nicholas II is in the centre, the Princess Olga
At the bottom of the cover page: Chernomorskaya Guberniya (Black Sea Province) emblem
and photo “Views of the Russian Empire”

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Kharkiv Educational District (1803–1917): A Review of Modern Historiography

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Abstract

The article considers an overview of modern historiography devoted to the Kharkiv Educational District (1803–1917). 43 English-language and Russian-language publications made in the period from 2006 to 2024 are analyzed.

The research methodology is based on the historical and genetic method, which allowed the authors to consider the evolution of the study of the public education system on the territory of the Kharkiv Educational District. The great importance is also given to the historical and systemic method, thanks to which the authors considered the studied problem comprehensively, taking into account the established traditions in historiography. At the same time, the authors applied a comparative historical method that allowed them to pay attention to the specifics of conducting scientific research on the Kharkiv Educational District.

The presented review of modern historiography shows that the system of public education in the territory of the Kharkiv Educational District is now actively engaged in the Cherkas Global University, which is implementing an ambitious project “The system of public education in the Russian Empire: a historical and statistical study”. As part of this project, the organization's staff comprehensively reviewed the public education systems of all six territories of the Kharkiv Educational District. Besides this, representatives of regional historical scientific schools are currently engaged in various aspects of public education, which, as a rule, touch on private issues and rarely return to the public education system in their publications.

Keywords: historiography, Kharkiv Educational District, Ministry of Public Education, Russian Empire.

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Харьковский учебный округ (1803–1917 гг.): обзор современной историографии:

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Аннотация. В работе рассматривается обзор современной историографии, посвященный Харьковскому учебному округу (1803–1917 гг.). Анализируются 43 англоязычные и русскоязычные публикации, сделанные в период с 2006 по 2024 гг.

Методология исследования базируется на историко-генетическом методе, который позволил авторам рассмотреть эволюцию изучения системы народного образования на территории Харьковского учебного округа. Большое значение уделено и историко-системному методу, благодаря которому авторы рассмотрели изучаемую проблему комплексно с учетом сложившихся традиций в историографии. В тоже время авторы применили сравнительно-исторический метод, который позволил обратить внимание на специфику проведения научных исследований, посвященных Харьковскому учебному округу.

Представленный обзор современной историографии показывает, что системой народного образования на территории Харьковского учебного округа сегодня активно занимается Cherkas Global University, который реализует амбициозный проект «Система народного образования в Российской империи: историко-статистическое исследование». В рамках этого проекта сотрудниками организации были комплексно рассмотрены системы народного образования всех шести территорий Харьковского учебного округа. Кроме того, различными аспектами народного образования сегодня занимаются и представители региональных исторических научных школ, которые, как правило, затрагивают частные вопросы и редко возвращаются вновь в своих публикациях к системе народного образования.

Ключевые слова: историография, Харьковский учебный округ, Министерство народного просвещения, Российская империя.